

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IN LEARNING LANGUAGES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: Equality between men and women has made significant progress worldwide. However, gender concerns have not completely disappeared. Gender prejudice and discrimination are widespread in society and education. Accomplishing gender equality will always be a critical problem in education.

Key words: Gender Stereotypes; Education; Learning languages; Female Teenagers.

Introduction

Gender stereotypes are widespread perceptions, expectations, and requirements about male and female conduct regarding personality, attributes, and other elements. Gender stereotypes can lead people to oversimplify their understanding of gender groupings and hold incorrect beliefs. Gender stereotypes, for example, exaggerate the distinctions between men and women, contribute to prejudice against a particular group, or cause people to lose their identity. Eliminating gender stereotypes is critical for both individual and societal growth.

Education is one of the most important components in personal and societal development. Adolescence is critical for the development of self-knowledge. Many gender discrepancies in subject and profession selection are due to gender preconceptions rather than differences in ability between men and women. However, by identifying and addressing these gender stereotypes, we can bring about positive change in the education system, providing equal opportunities for all students.

Gender stereotyping is defined as "ascribing certain attributes, characteristics, and roles to people based on their gender" (UNICEF, 2017). More specifically, it entails assigning traditional gender norms based on one's assigned sex at birth. For example, ladies are expected to seek careers as nurses or teachers, whereas guys will pursue ambitions in science, engineering, or business and hold leadership positions. Gender stereotyping happens at home, school, and in society.

Gender stereotyping begins in childhood and becomes apparent early on (Gelman et al., 2004). According to studies, children learn gender stereotypes as early

as the age of two (Serbin et al., 2002; Shenouda & Danovitch, 2014), and by the age of four, most children have established a stable understanding of their gender identity and learned gender role behaviors (Brown et al., 2011). For example, the OECD's International Early Learning and Child Well-being Study discovered that gender norms are visible as early as the age of five. Boys aged five are less interested in historically more female-dominated positions than girls in traditionally male-dominated occupations.

Self-Confidence

During adolescence, boys and girls change self-confidence, although girls' self-confidence appears to be more adversely impacted, while boys tend to be more positively influenced. Girls were more susceptible to these gender norms than boys. Female students typically exhibit lower confidence and more melancholy symptoms in school, which is linked to gender norms in both academics and society. Putnam discovered that gender stereotype threats caused females to lose confidence and enthusiasm in one specific subject, eventually quitting and pursuing other interests.

Career Choices

Stereotypes that students experience frequently impact their employment selections. People's preconceived assumptions about women's abilities have resulted in exclusion or rejection from STEM areas. For instance, girls may be more inclined to believe that their mathematics skills are inferior to those of boys. Strong gender stereotypes have been connected to women's lesser interest in traditionally male-dominated occupations. Girls are more likely than males to major in "less profitable" disciplines like literature and art rather than pursue professions in Science, Technology, Engineering, or Mathematics (STEM), even though they have the potential to excel in these fields.

Social Identity

Gender stereotypes that make girls feel inferior and submissive will influence how they perceive themselves and their social identities. Gender stereotypes persist even in places with higher levels of education, such as universities, and will influence students' future successes. For example, women have been rejected from or driven out of STEM industries due to people's opinions of their abilities. According to one research, women talked less in seminar or tutorial classes and were constantly stopped by male students when they sought to express their ideas. Male students, on the other hand, reported feeling more at ease and confident speaking in class.

Conclusion

Gender stereotype study shows that girls and boys go through various socialization processes, including the gender stereotypes they face in their contexts. Families have the earliest and most direct impact on the development of teens' gender role views. When youngsters go to school, the components contributing to forming opinions grow broader and more complicated. In addition to instructors' perspectives on gender roles, which may directly or indirectly impact pupils' opinions, youngsters interact with their classmates in a more complex setting. Furthermore, the media may promote gender stereotypes among youngsters.

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